

THE PRIMES IN THE SMARANDACHE POWER PRODUCT SEQUENCES OF THE SECOND KIND

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Abstract. In this paper we completely determine the primes in the Smarandache power product sequences of the second kind.

Key words . Smarandache power product sequencem , second kind, prime.

For any positive integers n, r with $r > 1$, let $P(n, r)$ be the n -th power of degree r . Further, let

$$(1) \quad U(n, r) = \prod_{k=1}^n P(k, r) - 1.$$

Then the sequence $U(r) = \{U(n, r)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is called the Smarandache r -power product sequence of the second kind. In [2], Russo proposed the following question.

Question. How many terms in $U(2)$ and $U(3)$ are primes?

In this paper we completely solve the mentioned question. We prove a more strong result as follows.

Theorem. If r and $2^r - 1$ are both primes, then $U(r)$ contains only one prime $U(2, r) = 2^r - 1$. Otherwise, $U(r)$ does not contain any prime.

Proof. Since $U(1, r) = 0$, we may assume that $n > 1$. By (1), we get

$$(2) \quad U(n, r) = (n!)^r - 1 = (n! - 1)((n!)^{r-1} + (n!)^{r-2} + \dots + 1).$$

Since $n! > 2$ if $n > 2$, we see from (2) that $U(n, r)$ is not a prime if $n > 2$. When $n = 2$, we get from (2) that

(3) $U(2,r)=2^r-1.$

Therefore, by [1,Theorem 18], we find from (3) that $U(r)$ contains a prime if and only if r and 2^r-1 are both primes. The theorem is proved.

References

- [1] G.H.Hardy and E.M.Wright, An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1937.
- [2] F.Russo, Some results about four Smarandache U-product sequences, Smarandache Notions J.11(2000),42-49.

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